

AGRICULTURAL FARM DAM FOR THE UNIVERSITY OF JOS: A RECONNAISSANCE SURVEY

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ABSTRACT

The total staff and students population of the University of Jos currently stands at over ten thousand. As a second generation University, it is still expanding its academic programmes. This indicates that this population shall continue to rise in the not-so-distant future demanding for more domestic and sundry water consumption which even at present is over-stretched. Of the several proposed Engineering Departments which include Mechanical, Mining/Metallurgy, Agricultural, /Veterinary Medicine, Civil and Computer/ Electronic Departments, the Agricultural Engineering Department stands out as the most readily demanding especially when viewed from its potential to effectively contribute to the development of agriculture in Plateau State and the nation at large. The pending contribution of the department to enhance the production of the ever- demanding temperate crops being grown on the Plateau such as Apples. Citrus fruits, potatoes variety of vegetables and fruits, rose-flowers etc cannot be over-emphasised. The construction of the Farm Dam will facilitate the establishment of an integrated Farm consisting of variety of livestock, aqua-culture/ fisheries, irrigation in addition to water supply amongst others. This is expected to be in harmony with the environment in line with best practices. From the fore-going therefore, it goes without gain saying that the construction of appropriate Farm Dam at the University's permanent Site to provide the much needed water for aqua-cultural and agricultural research , growth and development is apt and timely, requiring urgent intervention if possible by the Federal Government. A reconnaissance survey was carried out which included geological mapping, the study of sub-surface fractures of rocks, water-flow etc. Preliminary geological data obtained suggests that it is possible to establish a farm dam at the northern fringe of the stream channel flowing into the Delimi River.

KEYWORDS: Farm Dam, Tributaries, Irrigation, Geological Mapping, Stream channel, Watershed

METHODOLOGY

The reconnaissance study of the northern part of the Permanent Site became necessary in order to identify the water catchment terrain of the proposed dam site. The use of Google-Earth was employed in order to extract the map of the study area. The locations of the Mining Clusters were obtained from alluvial and primary deposits with the aid of GPS which was used to pick up the coordinates and then inserted on a Georeferenced map, using the software ILWIS 3.1 Academic. The digitized map was exported out of ILWIS 3.1 Academic into Microsoft word for further editing.

Geology

The area of study is bounded by lat $9^{\circ} 57' 30''$ N to $9^{\circ} 57' 10''$ N and long $8^{\circ} 52' 30''$ E- $8^{\circ} 53' 45''$ E. The area is generally underlain by the rocks of the Basement Complex consisting of migmatite and granite gneiss towards the western and central parts, and the Younger Granite (biotite granite) towards the eastern part of the study area (Lar et al 2012).

The Basement rocks here are well deformed with major structural trends in the NE-SW directions but also with appreciable NW-SE trending lineaments. Towards the eastern part, cooling joints can be seen on the Younger Granite (Fig.1)

Fig.1: Satellite Imagery

Geomorphology

The elevation is generally higher within the biotite granite along the western part with an average elevation of about 1200m above sea level. Within the basement complex, elevations are generally low, with a value of about 700m above mean sea level. From the satellite imagery, it appears as if the stream across which the dam is intended to be constructed is running along a major NW-SW trending fracture system. This fracture system may have also cause a minor displacement within the NE-SW trending fractures (Fig.2). This will have to be thoroughly investigated prior to the construction of the dam using multiple geophysical techniques (Resistivity, Electromagnetic and possibly Seismic method).

Fig.2: Fracture Map

Drainage and Climate

The drainage pattern here is dendritic (running almost in SSE-NNW direction), characterized by two major irregular tributaries(running from North western parts) with the head water originating from three major springs out of the southerly Younger granitic hills of Jos. There also exist three seasonal micro-tributaries flowing into the main stream from an EEW-direction all combining to flow into the Delimi River (Fig.3 &4).

Fig.3: Watershed/Drainage Map of the Site

Fig.4. Confluence of Stream Channel with the River Dilimi (red arrow)

The topography is gently sloping and sparsely covered with light agricultural plantations, shrubs and bushes. The dimensions of the stream is irregular about 3.5 metres in width and 1.2 metres deep upstream flowing at an average speed of 0.5 m/sec directly on the granitic basement rocks composed of mainly of migmatites and gneisses. The climate of this area is similar to what is obtainable on the Jos-Plateau and determined by the altitude and position across the seasonal migration of the Inter-tropical Convergent Zone (ITCZ). The wet season starts from April –October and the dry season from November -March. The mean annual rainfall here is about 1,240mm with a peak value of about 320mm in the month of August. The temperature around the area is equally high with a maximum of about 26°C – 28°C between the months of March and April. This is when evaporation is expected to be highest. The map shows that study area has its source from the country rock which is from a watershed or spring network connecting to the stream channel that will feed the proposed Dam. A spring is a natural opening in the ground where water flows directly from the aquifer to the earth's surface. The source of this fresh water is from seasonal rainfall that soaks into the ground, which is referred to as groundwater. Springs form when groundwater is under pressure and flows up through an opening called a *spring vent*, supplying flow to a river or other water body. A spring can occur individually or as a group of many springs forming the watershed. A watershed is the area of land where all of the water that is under it or drains off of it goes into the same place. In this case the water drains flowing out in form of three major springs behind the fence of the Naraguta Country Club (Fig.5).

Fig.5. Three main source of the water (springs) behind Naraguta Country Club
(N9°58'23.3" E08°53'01.9")

A recent study had estimated quantity of water required (demand) for students' hostels, staff quarters and campuses and other sundry requirement at 4,567,800 litres per day (Lar et al 2012). The estimation was based on the NUC standard water requirements in Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria which stipulates a capacity of 300 litres / head for campuses and offices and 600 litres /head for residence (Othman et al 1993; Lar et al 2011). It is evident that from natural disposition of the permanent site of the University, it is possible to achieve an integrated and sustainable water supply for the University's immediate needs while not conceding or compromising agricultural/aqua-cultural considerations. The proposed site of the Dam is shown in Fig.6.

Fig.6. Proposed Dam Site-Showing Micro-tributaries

The Proposed Farm Dam

Farm dams are water conservation structures designed to impound water using a constructed earth barrier or embankment that has a clay core or clay blanket keyed into impervious material and an excavation on the upslope side (Cunningham, 2011). Farm dams are used to provide long-term storage for: watering livestock; crop spraying; irrigation; domestic supply; and fire fighting and for aqua-culture and fisheries.

Most dams are constructed to store run-off generated from rainfall events. In other cases they are built as evaporation basins, and can also be used to store pumped groundwater. Farm dams are recognised as important structures for the management of problems associated with excess run-off.

The requirements of the expected dam based on the reconnaissance survey are as follows:

1. The proposed site is expected to provide a favourable storage to excavation ratio making the farm dam cost-effective;
2. The catchment area is large enough to allow the dam to maintain a reliable water supply relative to demand and evaporation loss. In this case spring water is flows all year round. The area contributing run-off to the dam in this case the existing tributaries can be maximised by improving the catchment. Half-roads have a broad flat channel with clay on the base and are one of the most effective methods of catchment improvement. With improved catchments, the area available to collect run-off from low rainfall events can be increased by lowering the threshold at which run-off is generated. The catchment condition will determine the quality of the water supply. The climate conditions which can guarantee minimising evaporation loss from prevailing winds are very favourable.
3. The water-holding properties of a farm dam are achieved using construction methods that provide a cover of reworked compacted clay on the base and sides. This clay blanket needs to be thick enough to provide a seal so that only small amounts of seepage are lost. Provided dams are sited to optimise the slope of the natural catchment above them, run-off from this catchment will flow unobstructed into them. Livestock will not have direct access to dam water. Livestock are expected to be watered using

an outlet pipe from the dam that will transfer the water to tanks and troughs on the downstream side of the dam.

4. The provision of a spillway to manage flows from both the natural and improved catchment;
5. Adequate geotechnical information of the sub-surface rocks to minimise seepage losses and ensure stability of the dam. While native vegetation is a good indicator of soil type, investigation for dam site selection needs to include drilling at least five holes, one at each corner and one in the centre of the proposed site. The test holes are drilled to at least 1 m below the proposed depth of the dam, to determine if shallow water tables are present and that the soil has satisfactory water-holding capability under the base of the dam. This analysis will assist in determining the water-holding capacity of the clay.
6. Estimates for storage volumes in litres at the proposed site (Cummings, 1999) can be made using the following formula:

$$V_g = (d \times w \times l) / 3000 + V_e$$

Where:

V_g = Total volume of water stored behind bank
(Megalitres, ML)

d = depth of water adjacent to bank (m) but not including excavation depth

w = width of water body at full supply level adjacent to bank (m)

l = length of water body from bank to inflow point (m)

V_e = Volume of excavation below full supply level (ML).

The study intends to have one Farm dam in addition to a couple of off-stream tanks/dams like Ring tanks/dams, excavated tanks and turkey nest tanks (Ring tanks); which should serve various purposes for livestock, aquaculture/ fisheries and for irrigation amongst others. Incidentally such tanks have already been constructed by the University and lies down-stream of the proposed dam-site. The choice of primary Farm dam in combination with smaller off-stream dams and location for each dam depends on several factors including technical feasibility, location of water deficit areas that need to be serviced and other alternatives available for agricultural and sundry purposes.

Environmental Concerns

Environmental concerns for wildlife conservation and vegetation shall be given attention in line with obtainable best practices; to the effect that the project shall see wildlife conservation as an important secondary use for farm dams. The study therefore seeks to incorporate dam design features that allow multiple uses, e.g. stock water, habitat for water-birds and/or fish, and refuge for native animals during dry times. Vegetation, including trees planted at sufficient distance from the dam, can provide windbreaks which reduce wave action (and hence bank erosion) as well as reducing evaporation. At the same time they provide shelter for wildlife in addition to any rare and threatened flora and fauna species in line with standing national environmental Protection and Biodiversity Conservation. Shrubs, trees or other deep rooted plants would not be allowed to establish within 5 meters, of the anticipated height of the mature growth of the dam embankments or spillway in order to avoid pathways for leakage through the dam wall and which may result in dam failure. From the geological and fracture maps available in this study, the proposed Farm Dam and off-stream water storage tanks are unlikely to be located in areas prone to erosion or areas that are ecologically sensitive.

Climatic conditions would normally trigger wind-borne dung and other organic materials to be blown or washed into the farm dam. Rain-storms can also wash such materials into dams. Once in the water, the organic materials provide ideal food for bacteria and algae. These organisms grow rapidly using up all free oxygen in the water by becoming anaerobic. Symptoms are dark water, a bad smell and black scum around the edge which would make the water unpalatable for livestock. As a remediation measure the project would:

- i) Maintain vegetation (e.g. grasses and shrubs) around the dam so that it is effectively able to filter and trap wind-and water-borne organic matter.
- ii) Fence to restrict stock access and protect filter vegetation.
- iii) Shelter the dam from direct movement of wind-and water-borne organic matter by temporary mechanical barriers around strategic parts of the dam.
- iv) Skim floating organic material and scum from the farm dam before it sinks.
- v) Dislodge sunken materials from the edges of the dam, and the bottom if possible.
- vi) Aerate and/or chemically treat anaerobic water if it is urgently needed for stock or domestic use and
- vii) Monitor water quality (e.g. salinity, nutrient pollution and palatability to stock).

Ideally, livestock should not have direct access to dam water. Livestock should be watered using an outlet pipe from the dam that transfers the water to tanks and troughs. Water troughs can be monitored quickly and easily from the farm office, using a photographic monitoring technique and water level sensors that provide information for all water supplies.

Procedure for Construction

Items involved in the construction of the Farm Dam are as follows:

1. Desk study. The Desk study shall involve the following activities; purchase of maps, past reports, satellite imageries, annual rainfall data, evaporation rate data, drainage system pattern, and water shed study of water table conditions etc.
2. Geological, Geophysical and Geotechnical investigations (site investigations) will include Pitting, drilling of exploratory holes sampling from the trial pits, laboratory testing and foundations analysis.
3. Dam site selection and survey. Preparation of a plan and cross-section. These plans allow realistic comparison between different needs.
4. Equipment selection and Design of Farm Dam. Equipment selection:- Scrappers; Excavators; Dump trucks ;Percussion drill machine ;Compactor; Blasting accessories; Concrete mixers ;4 wheel drive pickups and Grouting pumps etc.
5. Construction:- Construction of the in addition to removal of over burden ; excavation to bedrock ; embankment apron, barricade, stone pitching, off-stream water tanks etc.

Findings

1. Information on preliminary site investigation at the disposal of this study on geological mapping, the drainage pattern , Rock Fractures and constant source of underground water which are critical parameters in dam construction, indicate very favourable conditions for the construction of a Farm Dam within the University land at the Permanent Campus. The construction of additional off-stream water storage facilities can further support the various agricultural water needs of the University.
2. The proposed Dam which is expected to be sighted across the Naraguta dendritic stream channel at a distance of about 1.5km North of the Senate Building of the University, at the Permanent Campus (by the confluence of the stream channel with the Delimi River) shall not only provide the much needed water supply but is also expected to provide the following: a). Pilot irrigation/animal husbandry and aquatic/fisheries land down stream, especially for the Faculty of Agriculture/Veterinary Medicine. b). A serene wetlands environment and/ or sanctuary infrastructures for tourism and recreation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Establishing a new dam is a water affecting activity (WAA) which requires strict adherence to environmental concerns to guard against potential impacts to sensitive water-dependent ecosystems. That the establishment of a new faculty of engineering and particularly the Departments of Agriculture and Veterinary Medicine, requires the construction of a University Farm Dam requiring immediate intervention by the Federal Government.

That in order to fully achieve afore mentioned recommendations, there is the need for an in-depth geotechnical investigation of the proposed Dam Site.

CONCLUSION

The reconnaissance survey supports the establishment of Farm dam at the permanent campus of the University of Jos. In pursuing this objective, there is the need to further carry out an in-depth geological and geotechnical investigation of the sub-structure of the soils and rocks with the sole intention of embracing the sound principles of socio-economic values and environmental management. The Farm Dam shall provide an essential component of overall and integrated water management systems. It shall divert water, retain it over long periods of time to use it effectively and it shall attenuate any floods and alleviate impacts of droughts. The dam shall relieve drainage congestion, and provide for the timely and continuous supply of irrigation water needed to meet the demands of crops and livestock of the proposed new Departments of Agriculture/Veterinary Medicine and domestic water supply. A judicious combination of smaller off-stream water storage facilities may be required for storage of water, withdrawal and use same within minimum transport distance to demand sections of the new Departments and residential areas of the University.

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